

A Comprehensive Plan for Studying the Carbon Cycle from Space

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Abstract— During 2001, a team of scientists and engineers from NASA Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC) led a planning activity for future studies of the sources, sinks, and transport of carbon in the atmosphere, on land, and in the oceans. This study was conducted at the request of NASA Headquarters. Members of the Earth sciences community and representatives from other NASA centers and Headquarters participated in a series of workshops to further refine the science questions, determine the required measurements, and identify gaps in our current measurement suite.

Three critical gaps were identified: (1) Global time series of CO₂ atmosphere-surface exchange, (2) Ecosystem carbon storage due to land biomass and its change as well as the carbon consequences of disturbance and (3) Measurements of critical biochemicals mediating global ocean surface layer uptake and export of carbon. The observations required to fill these gaps were also defined and include: (1) Satellite-based observations of column and profile carbon dioxide concentration, (2) Reprocessing of the historic land satellite record to track land use changes over time and quantify their carbon consequences, (3) Satellite-based measurement of low density and high density biomass, and (4) Satellite measurement of chlorophyll and related organic and inorganic compounds in the coastal and upper deep ocean.

The status of observation technology to support these new measurements was investigated through detailed science and engineering studies, and developed into nominal missions in the Goddard Integrated Mission Design Center. Technologies are currently not at a high enough technology readiness level to support all of these missions. A program of technology development with priorities was recommended.

Algorithm development, historical data analysis, in situ and aircraft measurements, field campaigns, calibration and

validation requirements, numerical model and data assimilation development, and data synthesis were also included in the recommendations. The various elements were costed, prioritized, and provided to NASA Headquarters for consideration. This material was presented to OMB and subsequent activities have benefited from this planning effort.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. CARBON CYCLE OVERVIEW.....	1
2. DEFINITION STRATEGY.....	2
3. MISSION CONCEPTS.....	6
4. TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT RQMTS.....	11
5. LASER TECHNOLOGY READINESS.....	14
6. CRITICAL DEPENDENCIES.....	15
7. SUMMARY.....	16
8. UPDATE.....	17
REFERENCES.....	17

1. CARBON CYCLE OVERVIEW

While variations in the Earth's climate are caused by a number of factors external to the climate system (land-ocean-atmosphere), including variations in the Earth's orbit about the sun, the orientation of its rotational axis with respect to the Earth-Sun plane, and even variations in the intensity of the sun's radiant output, major regulators of climate change are "internal", including processes associated with the carbon cycle and photosynthesis (Figure 1). Warming of the Earth's climate is driven primarily by the absorption of solar energy by heat-absorbing biologically generated "greenhouse" gases such as carbon dioxide and methane, and light-absorbing aerosols such as smoke and soot. Cooling results from reflective clouds and other aerosols such as dust. Removal of greenhouse gases by the Earth's terrestrial vegetation and its oceans by photosynthesis also acts to cool the Earth.

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Examining the Earth's carbon budget, the climate-carbon connection can be clearly seen. The annual increase in atmospheric CO₂ of about 3 petagrams/year results from the emission of nearly 7 petagrams/year of carbon from the combustion of fossil fuels. However, roughly half is absorbed each by the land (2 petagrams/year) and oceans (2 petagrams/year), resulting in a much slower increase in atmospheric carbon dioxide. Thus, these natural ecosystems provide a service to the global economy worth billions of dollars through natural mitigation of climate change. The reasons for this capacity of the Earth's land and oceans to absorb carbon dioxide are not adequately understood, and future uptake by the land and oceans cannot be estimated. Given the importance of forecasting climate change to the nation, it is of utmost urgency to find out.

Figure 1. Carbon Cycle: Living With a Planet

2. DEFINITION STRATEGY

In April of 2000, NASA Headquarters charged the GSFC to lead a team consisting of the science community, NASA Headquarters representatives, NASA center representatives, and other agency representatives, to develop a NASA-wide Global Carbon Cycle Plan (GCCP). The plan would need to define a science and technical roadmap to focus NASA's current space assets, carbon cycle science programs, and facilities on improving our understanding of the global carbon cycle and provide information products supporting decision makers and the user community. The plan would also need to identify, cost and prioritize any new science programs, space missions or facilities required. The plan would define program success criteria, that is, performance metrics against which to gauge the future progress and accomplishments of the effort in terms of its stated goals.

The plan definition process formally began in the fall of 2000 with the selection of a Science Working Group and the announcement of the process to define the GCCP. GSFC and Wallops Flight Facility (WFF) scientists worked

with the other organizations participating in the definition phase. These included: (1) the NASA center representatives from (Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL), Ames Research Center (ARC), Langley Research Center (LaRC), Marshall Space Flight Center (MSFC), Kennedy Space Center (KSC), and Stennis Space Center (SSC); (2) NASA Headquarters program office representatives (including managers of relevant programs in Codes Y, S, and U); (3) a Science Working Group (SWG) and, (4) the carbon cycle Interagency Working Group (IWG) of the US Global Change Research Program (USGCRP). The GSFC team, assisted by these other groups, conducted the necessary studies to define new science programs, facilities and mission requirements, and costs. The GSFC team consisted of personnel from GSFC Codes 910, 920, 930, 940 and 970 as well as representatives from the project formulation office within Code 740.

The proposal definition process itself consisted of three workshops and a number of GSFC studies to investigate mission concept feasibility (Figure 2). The workshops consisted of joint plenary sessions and separate science discipline break-out discussions. Each discipline break-out had a discussion leader and a rapporteur. After each workshop, the discussion leaders submitted summaries.

The focus of the first workshop held at the GSFC January 9-11 2001, was to define the science questions the NASA GCCP would need to address, the information products that would need to be produced, the performance metrics that such products would need to satisfy and what NASA's potential new contributions would be in the context of other agency efforts. It was then agreed to accept the science questions that had been articulated in "A US Carbon Cycle Science Plan" by J. Sarmiento and S. Wofsy (1999), under the auspices of the USGCRP. Information products in the broadest terms would consist of locating and quantifying the magnitudes of global carbon sources and sinks as well as the remote sensing products that support such assessment. Part of the planning effort would be to use the GCCP modeling framework to better define just how accurate such products must be to improve existing information and to make useful assessments in support of US policy goals and thus the specific nature of the performance metrics. A major result of the first workshop was a community consensus as to the missing observations required to answer the science questions posed. These were identified as observations of high-spatial and temporal resolution atmospheric CO₂, terrestrial biomass and biomass change, ocean surface layer organic and inorganic carbon, air-sea CO₂ fluxes, and global land cover and land cover change products from Landsat.

Figure 2. Proposal Development Process

In addition, preliminary observational and technology approaches (observational requirements and instrument types) were defined for more detailed study between the first and second workshop.

The focus of the second workshop (March 20-22, 2001) was to define a NASA science and technology roadmap required to address the science questions in the context of existing agency capabilities. This roadmap is the set and sequence of activities and resources that would be required to develop the new observations and associated modeling and field programs needed to address the science questions, produce the information products and satisfy the performance metrics laid out in the first workshop. Also, as part of the preparation for the second workshop, the new measurements identified in the first workshop were linked with potential missions. These mission concepts were developed in greater detail and paired with appropriate spacecraft and launch vehicles in the Integrated Mission Design Center (IMDC) at GSFC. IMDC studies included an aerosol polarimeter, a CO₂ lidar, and an advanced land biomass lidar. This process examined the various subsystems as well and sought to identify any technology challenges by subsystem and for the mission as a whole. The results of these studies could then be used as a basis for costing potential missions with the assistance of the Resource Analysis Office (RAO) in preparation for the third workshop (May 2-4, 2001). This information could then serve as the basis for an informed prioritization of the

candidate science activities, both individually and in synergistic combinations.

The third workshop consisted of reviewing a draft GCCP, the science and technology roadmaps (activities, activity relationships, missions, schedules, resource requirements, etc.), and prioritizing missions and activities. It was agreed at the third workshop to initiate a series of telecons involving the carbon planning team to put together a presentation to the NASA Associate Administrator of the Office of Earth Sciences, Dr. Ghassem Asrar, and his staff. The formal presentation was on June 19, 2001, shortly after the President's call for climate research and technology initiatives. The recommendations for the GCCP were subsequently published in McClain et al. (2002) and Gervin et al. (2002). The science and technology roadmaps will be summarized in the following sections.

Science Roadmap

Coupled land, ocean and atmospheric carbon cycling models, driven and constrained by satellite and conventional observations, will form the carbon analysis framework of the GCCP. The general modeling framework will be structured around: (1) inversion models that exploit spatial and temporal variations in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations to track CO₂ transport from the land and ocean surface through the atmosphere, and (2) physical and biological process models that predict the exchange rates of CO₂ between the atmosphere's interface with land and ocean surfaces and the carbon transformations that occur within

each domain. Both modeling techniques are designed to infer regional magnitudes of net CO₂ exchange. They can be intercompared, and thus provide insight into (1) what has happened to the CO₂ that has already been emitted by human activities, (2) how land management and land use, terrestrial and ocean dynamics, and other factors affect carbon sources and sinks over time and, (3) how future atmospheric carbon dioxide concentrations might change as a result of environmental changes, human actions, and past and future emissions. These three endeavors are in essence the goals of the USGCRP Carbon Plan. Figure 3 provides an overview of the science roadmap that has been developed, and shows the activity blocks and timeline. The program needs to address the USGCRP science questions and goals and the research and observational requirements that derive from them. The activities, the horizontal bars, fall into three general groups. The top three bars represent either current space observations or activities to develop the new observational capabilities required. The second group, the next five activity bars, represents those activities required to convert the satellite radiances into observational parameters and the analysis and modeling capabilities, along with these observations, needed to address the questions and perform the necessary assessments. In particular, a North American field campaign is the first phase of a longer term North American Carbon Program (NACP) (Wofsy and Harriss, 2002) and will be central to developing, calibrating and validating advanced sensor techniques and algorithms.

The last four bars are those activities required to develop coupled physical-biogeochemical models with satellite and conventional data assimilation capabilities for conducting regional and global analyses, providing answers to the science questions and enabling projections and assessments.

The top activity bar of Figure 3, "Current/Planned Space Assets", expresses the assumption that the global data products from Terra, SeaWiFS and other currently operational sensors will be available from NASA's base program to the carbon cycle program. For Landsat data, however, a new requirement was defined, and that is to accelerate the analysis of global carbon-specific data products from Landsat, including land cover and land cover change maps and the production of global 30 meter land cover disturbance maps. This would require the automated classification of the global ortho-rectified Landsat data set being assembled by Earth Satellite Corporation from the 70's, the 90's and 2000. This activity would provide global information on natural and anthropogenic disturbance in each decade. From these maps, rates of disturbance, cause of disturbance, and age distribution would be produced at 30 meters and aggregated to appropriate scales (e.g., 10 km) for global carbon analyses. This data set will be key to addressing changes in ecosystem carbon stocks.

As shown in the third activity bar from the bottom, labeled "Data Synthesis", all relevant satellite data products, as well as other data necessary to the carbon analysis framework,

will need to be synthesized into global data sets, with a common grid and format, and provided to the GCCP science community for analysis.

New missions would occur no sooner than 2007, given a 5-year formulation cycle. Since the ongoing NASA Earth System Science Pathfinder (ESSP) process has selected the JPL-led Orbiting Carbon Observatory, which will provide a passive measurement of column CO₂ as well as the carbon-related Aquarius mission, new carbon missions could launch as early as 2006.

An important part of the GCCP is the model development activity that will focus on improved utilization of satellite data. Ecosystem land and ocean process models need significant development to properly utilize the new data sets that remote sensing satellites will make available. For example, we need a better understanding of the carbon consequences of disturbance, higher spatial resolution inversion models, improved inversion techniques, etc.

NASA participation in the field campaigns would focus on process model development, satellite sensor calibration, algorithm development, and satellite product validation. The GCCP would also include accelerated activities in the NACP, e.g., a field campaign in 2004 and 2005, and subsequent studies of tropical areas, Eurasia, and the southern oceans.

The science roadmap in Figure 3 is a summary of much more detailed roadmaps that were developed by the GSFC atmosphere, ocean, and land groups in collaboration with the GCCP team during the workshops. The roadmap is consistent with the research goals and objectives established by the NASA ESE and the USGCRP, but expands and accelerates particular, key activities that will substantially reduce uncertainties about future climate change.

Figure 3. GCCP Science Activity Roadmap

Technology Roadmap

An extensive evaluation of the technology readiness for each proposed observational concept has already been undertaken along with an assessment of observational feasibility. Figure 4 summarizes the mission concepts proposed for the GCCP which were studied in detail during the proposal definition phase. The next section contains detailed descriptions of the observational requirements and proposed instrument and mission concepts. These assessments have shown that reaching the stage of technological readiness required for an on-orbit demonstration of the concepts for the new measurements will need a careful, stepwise progression of technology, algorithm development (for extracting the necessary observations), and validation. Some of the capabilities (e.g., the CO₂ Light Detection and Ranging (Lidar)) are in the laboratory demonstration phase, while others, such as the Ocean Carbon Mission, have had instruments of similar capability or complexity (passive optical) demonstrated on orbit. Regardless, all new GCCP space observation technology developments will be supported, when it is deemed necessary and useful, by laboratory, field, and aircraft instrument demonstrations and intensive field program validation. Before any observational concept is deemed ready for space demonstration, it will be subjected to a step-wise series of rigorous tests and evaluations. It is

anticipated that the earliest any of the new observational capabilities could be deployed would be at least three years for very mature technologies, e.g., Ocean Carbon Mission, and five years or longer for less mature ones.

Given these realities, it would be premature at this stage in the planning to specify the timing for the new GCCP capabilities or launch schedules. However, for planning purposes, Figure 5 provides a "notional" set of mission schedules and the requisite technology development "wedges" leading up to the space-based deployments of science observational missions and/or demonstration missions. A launch date of 2005 is shown for a first vegetation canopy height lidar (VCL) mission. Late 2005 is possible only because development of VCL technology has been pursued over the past few years under the ESSP program. To accurately measure the rate of biomass recovery will actually require follow-on measurements to assess change and, possibly, two measurement approaches: one for low density biomass and one for high density biomass. VCL, if/when it flies, would be the first of these biomass sensors. It would take about 18 months for VCL to record the first global biomass survey, improving the accuracy of our knowledge of land biomass by a factor of 20 or more. An advanced high density biomass mission is tentatively scheduled five years following VCL, provided that VCL is successful, and will map the changes in global

biomass that have occurred in the intervening period. The advanced high density biomass satellite will incorporate some technology changes to extend the range of ecosystems observable with the single-frequency lidar flown aboard VCL, particularly the northern, high-latitude ecosystems that are important players in the global carbon cycle. A series of aircraft missions beginning in 2003/4 will explore advanced biomass technologies (high and low density), including dual-frequency lidars, hyperspectral radiometers, and radar. The biomass change design will be based on the results of these experiments and what is learned from VCL.

It is important to obtain improved estimates of spatial and temporal variability of atmospheric CO₂ as soon as possible. It appears that such observations can be obtained most quickly with a pathfinder CO₂ sounder, based on a passive sensor technology. With a 2003 GCCP start, the pathfinder could be ready for demonstration in five years, i.e., 2008. A mission lifetime of 5 years is proposed to observe useful interannual variations in land and ocean sinks and sources to correlate with climate variations induced by phenomena such as the El Nino-Southern Oscillation (ENSO). An advanced CO₂ lidar sounder is proposed to overlap one year with the pathfinder. We assume that the greater resolution and higher accuracy of a lidar approach will be needed. In comparison to the pathfinder, the advanced sounder will provide CO₂ information closer to the Earth's surface, at a different time of the day, and with less interference from clouds. The lidar, unlike the passive sounder that relies on the sun as its illumination source, will be able to obtain CO₂ concentrations nearer the Earth's surface, where the surface-induced CO₂ signal is stronger. In addition, because it provides its own illumination, the lidar can measure column CO₂ near dawn and dusk when column CO₂ measurements are easier to relate to surface-atmosphere exchange. Finally, cloud interference is much less at dawn and dusk, thus CO₂ concentrations could be obtained on a more frequent basis. Results from both the passive and active aircraft CO₂ instruments as well as the CO₂ pathfinder will be used to decide if the lidar is justified in terms of how accurately and how finely regional sources and sinks can be located.

New ocean observations would be possible in 2009 and 2010, one focusing on global carbon exchange with the open ocean, the Ocean Carbon Mission described earlier, and the second, a combined coastal ocean-land mission based on high resolution passive radiometry, to observe low density terrestrial biomass and carbon uptake at the land-ocean interface, a region long overlooked in quantifying carbon exchange. The coastal ocean observations are consistent (time of day, resolution, etc.) with those for observing low terrestrial biomass density, where lidar and radar technology do not perform well. To extend the range of global terrestrial biomass observations to medium and high density biomass regions and dramatically improve the sampling density, a high density biomass mission is envisioned for 2011. This is a logical follow-on to the VCL

and a low density biomass mission and would incorporate the lessons learned to improve our ability to obtain accurate measures of biomass and biomass change over a complete range of global ecosystems.

Observational accuracy requirements are stringent and will require investments in both technology, and research and development. A comprehensive field program will be conducted to develop satellite observation algorithms, calibrate the new sensors, and validate their data products. The GCCP will leverage off the programs already being conducted by other federal agencies which can provide validation data (e.g., the (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) CO₂ flask network, the US Forest Service (USFS) forest inventory), shipboard measurement opportunities, joint model development and evaluation activities, and others. Advanced analysis capabilities and models will be developed to take maximum advantage of the new observations. Models as they currently exist, must be improved to utilize the full power, resolution, and detail of the new observations. The GCCP will employ both observations and modeling to optimize predictions of carbon cycle and climate processes and responses.

3. MISSION CONCEPTS

An initial set of observational goals and requirements were established in the proceedings of several early GCCP workshops. With these as a starting point, the project formulation and systems engineering team began its work to develop a number of space mission candidates that would provide the desired measurements. Rough concepts were first developed and then definition studies were performed. Various sources were employed in this concept generation including related university, industry, and government studies. These studies evolved into a representative or baseline set of five space missions endorsed by the science team and described in the paragraphs that follow. Table 1 provides a summary of assumed measurement requirements for these studies.

The duration of the space measurements/missions discussed below is at least three years, technology permitting, in order to acquire information over more than one year. This will generally counteract the effect of a single unusual year by balancing it with two presumably normal years. Orbits are assumed to be standard low-earth orbits (400-700 km), generally sun-synchronous to remove the effects of diurnal variation in illumination and sun angle. Measurements from existing missions which are crucial to the carbon cycle work and from planned missions which represent critical dependencies are also shown on the timeline. For missions with instruments operating in the ultraviolet, visible, and near-infrared, the missions are to include monthly lunar calibration measurements similar to those of the Orbview-2/SeaWiFS mission, i.e., full lunar images at a constant phase angle. Key technology and aircraft/field campaigns

needed to support the spaceborne measurements are also highlighted.

Pathfinder Atmospheric CO₂ Mission Concept (Figure 6)

The consensus of the carbon cycle science team was that a pathfinder mission to make high precision (1 to 2 ppmv) global measurements of atmospheric column CO₂ abundance should be viewed as a top priority. Although a number of different measurement techniques exist, a concept was proposed that used a passive spectrometer with 10 km resolution. High signal-to-noise ratio detection of both CO₂ and O₂ during the daytime portion of the orbit is required. Several small, low-cost, three-axis stabilized, nadir-pointing spacecraft were found in the NASA GSFC Rapid Spacecraft Development Office (RSDO) catalog that could accommodate the instrument with adequate mass and power margins. A 500 to 700 km polar, sun-synchronous orbit with a late morning crossing time would provide the appropriate altitude and environmental conditions for data collection. A Pegasus XL or equivalent class launch vehicle was deemed adequate for this mission concept. Orbital life was proposed as three years.

Ocean Carbon Mission Concept (Figure 7)

Comprehensive observations of the world's oceans in the ultraviolet, visible, and near infrared portions of the electromagnetic spectrum are required for investigations of the marine biosphere, its variability, dynamics, and biogeochemical cycles. Enhancing and continuing the measurements initiated by the Nimbus-7/CZCS, Orbview-2/SeaWiFS, and EOS/MODIS instruments are critical in establishing the role played by the oceanic biosphere in the global carbon cycle.

The proposed ocean carbon mission is a small satellite mission that meets the above scientific objectives by making those ocean color measurements required for determination of ocean biomass, primary productivity, and dissolved organic matter. Irradiance measurements in 10 spectral bands from the ultraviolet to the near infrared are made by a rotating, scanning telescope equipped with an on-board solar calibrator. A small, low-cost, three-axis stabilized, nadir-pointing spacecraft provides the platform for the instrument telescope and associated electronics. A propulsion system is employed for orbit raising after launch by a Pegasus XL or equivalent, as well as for orbit maintenance and maneuvers. One such maneuver is a monthly spacecraft rotation essential for lunar calibration of the instrument. A 705 km polar, sun-synchronous orbit with a 12:00 noon crossing time is ideal. For planning purposes, a five-year mission lifetime has been assumed. In-situ measurements from ships and optical buoys provide additional calibration and validation data for comparison with the spaceborne instrumentation.

Low Density Biomass/Coastal Ocean Mission Concept (Figure 8)

Satellite observations provide the only practical means to obtain a synoptic view of the Earth's ecosystems along with their spatial distribution and temporal dynamics. Four priority areas have been identified where improved space-based measurements would significantly reduce the uncertainties in the global carbon budget. These include: (1) land cover characterization at higher spatial resolution, (2) above-ground biomass estimates, (3) areal estimates of disturbance and recovery, and (4) improved estimates of terrestrial and coastal ocean productivity.

In order to achieve the scientific objectives outlined above, a concept was developed for a low density biomass/coastal ocean mission that carries an advanced hyperspectral imager with heritage traceable to the Hyperion instrument demonstrated on the Lewis and NMP EO-1 missions. Active systems such as lidars are of limited use over grasslands and sparsely vegetated areas. The proposed instrument has a high signal-to-noise ratio detection system and covers a frequency range from 360 to 2350 nm. The instrument contains a SWIR spectrometer element with a bandwidth of 10 nm and a VNIR spectrometer with a bandwidth of 5 nm. Several candidate low-cost, three-axis stabilized, nadir-pointing spacecraft were identified that met instrument requirements with margin. However, some modification to the standard spacecraft Command and Data Handling (C&DH) and communications subsystems is anticipated in order to accommodate the inherently high data rates associated with hyperspectral sensing. A propulsion system was also included in the configuration to allow for orbit maintenance and for possible formation flying with other land imaging platforms. A 705 km sun-synchronous orbit with a 10:30 am descending node was the orbit of choice. A Taurus launch vehicle or equivalent was judged to be adequate for the integrated payload described above. A mission life of five years was chosen in order to provide a period of time sufficient for monitoring biomass change.

	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	10	11	12	Post 2012
							Aerosols					
ATMOSPHERE												
CO ₂ , CH ₄ , CO		MOPITT (Terra)					Pathfinder CO ₂					
		AIRS (Aqua)										
		TES (Aura)		CrIS (NPP)				Advanced CO ₂				
OCEAN												
SEA SURFACE - AIR EXCHANGE		QuikScat										
Organic/Inorganic Flux/Stocks		MODIS (Terra) MODIS (Aqua)				VIIRS (NPP)		VIIRS (NPOESS)				
POC/DOC/PIC/DIC		SeaWiFS					Ocean Carbon					
							LD Biomass/Coastal Ocean					
LAND												
VEGETATION BIOMASS						VCL				HD Biomass		
LAND COVER/LAND USE		Landsat, MODIS/MISR (Terra)		Landsat Follow-on, VIIRS (NPP)			VIIRS (NPOESS)					
TECHNOLOGY DEVELOP. WEDGE		Mission concept studies, insitu and A/C instrument/algorithm development										
COLLABORATIVE MISSIONS												
BASE ESE PROGRAM												
GCCP MISSION												

Figure 4. GCCP Technology Activities Roadmap

Pathfinder CO₂

Mission Life:
5 Years

Orbit: 705 km polar, sun-synchronous, with a 12:00 noon crossing time

Launch Vehicle:
Pegasus XL or equivalent

Mission Options: Single dedicated mission or as a complementary instrument on the Ocean Carbon mission.

Ocean Carbon

Mission Life:
5 Years

Orbit: 705 km polar, sun-synchronous, with a 12:00 noon crossing time

Launch Vehicle:
Pegasus XL or equivalent

Mission Options: A single instrument mission or a combined mission that includes the Pathfinder CO₂ measurement.

Low Density Biomass Coastal Ocean

Mission Life:
5 Years

Orbit: 705 km circular sun-synchronous with a 10:30 a.m. descending node

Launch Vehicle:
Taurus or equivalent

Key Technologies: Large area focal plane arrays, large capacity on-board recorders, and high rate downlink systems.

High Density Biomass

Mission Life:
3 Years

Orbit: 400 km polar sun-synchronous with a 6:00 p.m. ascending node

Launch Vehicle: Delta II or equivalent

Key Technologies: P-band polarimetric SAR, pixelated detectors, high-accuracy attitude & position package, laser diode & life-time improvement, & an S-band low power transceiver.

Advanced CO₂

Mission Life:
3 Years

Orbit: 590 km circular sun-synchronous with a 7:00 a.m. or 7:00 p.m. ascending node

Launch Vehicle: Delta 2320-10 or equivalent class launch vehicle

Key Technologies: 1570 nm lidar sensor, S-band low power transceiver.

Figure 5. Nominal Set of GCCP Missions

Table 1. Assumed Measurement Requirements

Measurement	Characteristic	Spatial Resolution	Spectral Range	Precision Accuracy	Temporal Frequency	Orbit
Atm. CO ₂	Column	10 km	VNIR	1-2 ppmv	Monthly	Daytime
	Profile	100 km, 3 layers	Lidar - NIR		Monthly	Dawn-Dusk
Ocean Carbon	DOC	1 km	UV		Daily	Daytime
	Fluorescence	1 km	NIR		Daily	Daytime
Land Biomass	Low Density	10 m - 250 m	VNIR SWIR		2 weeks	Daytime
	High Density	0.5 m vertical	Lidar, SAR		2 weeks	Dawn-Dusk

Note: Sun synchronous (unless otherwise stated), low earth orbits, and mission duration of at least 3 years (technology permitting) assumed.

- ◆ **Description:** A small satellite mission that makes high-precision (1 to 2 ppmv) global measurements of atmospheric column CO₂ abundance
- ◆ **Instrument:** A passive spectrometer with a 10 km spatial resolution that provides high signal-to-noise ratio detection of atmospheric CO₂ and O₂ during the day time portion of the orbit
- ◆ **Spacecraft:** A small, low-cost, three-axis stabilized, nadir pointing spacecraft from the RSDO catalog with a small propulsion system

Key Technologies:

S-Band LPT and other enhancing technologies at the subsystem or component level

Launch Date: FY 2008

Mission Life: 3 Years

Orbit: 500 to 700 km polar, sun-synchronous, with a morning crossing time

Launch Vehicle: Pegasus XL or equivalent class launch vehicle

Mission Options: Obtain through ESSP program or as a complementary instrument on the Ocean Carbon mission

Figure 6. Pathfinder Atmospheric CO₂

- ◆ **Description:** A small satellite mission that makes those ocean color measurements critical to the determination of ocean biomass, primary productivity, and dissolved organic matter
- ◆ **Instrument:** A rotating, scanning telescope equipped with an on-board solar calibrator that makes irradiance measurements in 10 spectral bands from the ultraviolet to the near infrared; additional bands or complementary hyperspectral instrument to obtain coastal ocean data
- ◆ **Spacecraft:** A small, low-cost, three-axis stabilized, nadir pointing spacecraft from the RSDO catalog with a propulsion system for orbit raising, maintenance, and maneuvers

Key Technologies: Selection of bands not generally used in land applications, improvements in sensor design, and the use of onboard data processing to optimize data retrieval

Launch Date: FY 2009
Mission Life: 5 Years
Orbit: 705 km polar, sun-synchronous, with a 12:00 noon crossing time
Launch Vehicle: Pegasus XL or equivalent class launch vehicle
Mission Options: A single instrument mission as outlined above or a combined mission that includes the Pathfinder Atmospheric CO₂ measurement

Figure 7. Ocean Carbon

- ◆ **Description:** A satellite mission that provides a synoptic view of the Earth's ecosystems, their spatial distribution, and temporal dynamics with global measurements of land cover, land cover change, and ocean surface chlorophyll
- ◆ **Instrument:** A hyperspectral imager providing high signal-to-noise ratios and covering a frequency range from 450 to 2350 nm with a SWIR bandwidth of 10 nm and a VNIR bandwidth of 5 nm
- ◆ **Spacecraft:** A low-cost, three-axis stabilized, nadir pointing spacecraft from the RSDO catalog with a propulsion system sized to allow formation flying with other land imaging platforms

Key Technologies: Large area focal plane arrays, large capacity on-board recorders, and high rate downlink systems for improved mission performance

Launch Date: FY 2010
Mission Life: 5 Years
Orbit: 705 km circular sun-synchronous with a 10:30 a.m. descending node
Launch Vehicle: Taurus or equivalent class launch vehicle

Figure 8. Low Density Biomass/Coastal Ocean

High Density Biomass Mission Concept (Figure 9)

Although a number of discrete space assets for land remote sensing exist, the science team desired a mission that would simultaneously improve regional and global estimates of vegetation biomass and carbon stocks, measure the response of terrestrial ecosystems to major disturbances, and monitor rates of recovery. Disturbances, as defined in this context, include both very rapid processes, such as fires and catastrophic windstorms, and more incremental changes from land-use intensification, acid deposition, and insect infestations.

Because hyperspectral measurements are of limited utility for biomass measurements in forests, an active system was considered. A mission concept was proposed that employed two flight instruments to provide the desired biomass measurements. These included a P-band SAR operating at 0.44 GHz and a multi-track, 1.064 micron, imaging laser altimeter with a capability of resolving 0.5 m differences in vegetation height. A three-axis stabilized, nadir-pointing spacecraft was required to accommodate the referenced instruments. Either a spacecraft from the RSDO catalog with appropriate modifications or another spacecraft with extensive flight heritage could be used. A large propulsion system for orbit maintenance and disposal and an X-band phased array for downlink of science data could be part of the final configuration. A 400 km polar, sun-synchronous orbit with a 6:00 pm ascending node was tentatively selected. Launch of the integrated payload requires a Delta II or equivalent vehicle in order to meet mass and volume expectations with margin. A mission lifetime of three years provides sufficient data to meet measurement objectives.

Advanced Atmospheric CO₂ Mission Concept (Figure 10)

Knowledge of global atmospheric CO₂ distribution in the lower troposphere is essential for understanding the carbon cycle and for solving the missing carbon sink mystery. Presently, however, atmospheric CO₂ is very poorly sampled. In order to address this deficiency, a study was performed in the GSFC IMDC to develop an advanced mission concept that measured CO₂ and O₂ column extinction from laser surface echoes. This sounding technique, based on GLAS/ICESAT instrument heritage, uses a pulsed, dual frequency, tunable laser operating in the 1570 nm band for carbon dioxide detection and in the 770 nm band for oxygen detection. A few low-cost, three-axis stabilized, nadir-pointing spacecraft were identified in the RSDO catalog that could meet instrument accommodation requirements with modest modifications, particularly to the power and propulsion subsystems. A 590 km polar, sun-synchronous orbit with either a 7:00 am or 7:00 pm ascending node provided a suitable environment from which to make the desired measurements. Launch to orbit was by means of a Delta 2320-10 or equivalent vehicle. A three-year mission life was considered sufficient to meet science objectives.

Instrument options at a lower level of technology readiness, but with vertical profiling capability, include a coherent laser absorption spectrometer or a differential absorption lidar each operating at a frequency of about 2 microns. Mission studies for these alternatives have been conducted by the JPL and LaRC teams, respectively.

4. TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT RQMTS.

The GCCP plans to utilize a number of active and passive sensor types to meet its ground, air, and space-based observational requirements. Experience to date with new flight systems indicates that technology readiness is a critical ingredient for program success. In order to minimize the risk associated with such systems, the GCCP study team has identified technology pathways for key instrumentation and has outlined a risk mitigation strategy to increase the probability of achieving the scientific goals and objectives within the cost and schedule guidelines.

The GCCP program intends to leverage existing technology programs like SBIR, ATIP, IIP, NMP and ESSP, wherever possible. It is also seeking focused technology development augmentations to ensure that critical instrumentation moves without interruption up the technology readiness chain. As part of the technology needs identification process, a mission/technology subgroup worked closely with atmosphere, ocean, and land working groups and performed benchmarking studies to highlight the most significant sensor development challenges. An assessment of specific atmosphere, ocean, and land sensor technology needs is given in the paragraphs that follow.

Atmospheric CO₂ Technology Requirements

A number of passive techniques for CO₂ column measurements were identified and were categorized broadly as either optical or thermal in nature. Some technology development is needed to improve signal to noise ratios and quantum efficiencies for photodiode arrays and mercury/cadmium/telluride detectors. In addition, larger detector arrays, if available, would substantially improve data return from space. Algorithms for combined CO₂/O₂ retrieval in a cloudy, aerosol-laden atmosphere and algorithms that accurately account for effects of varying pressure and temperature, surface reflectance, and other absorbers are additional development challenges.

Three active techniques for CO₂ profiling were also identified, one of which was the subject of a concept study in the GSFC IMDC and the other two in development by teams at LaRC and JPL. The GSFC approach utilizes a two-channel laser sounder in the 1570 nm band for carbon dioxide and the 770 nm band for oxygen. Lidar sensor development is a key technology and is already benefiting from some advanced technology funding via the ATIP program. The challenge is developing a CO₂ and O₂ lidar sensor with the required precision, stability, and lifetime for

a space mission. Because of projected power demands, the thermal control and heat rejection system will require careful consideration, although at the component level space qualified thermal control devices already exist. The LaRC Differential Absorption Lidar or DIAL approach to CO₂ global profiling employs a multiple DIAL pair technique and requires high-energy tunable laser transmitter technology development along with a large deployable receiver telescope. Infrared detector technology development is also critical to the success of space-based DIAL CO₂ measurements. Like the DIAL system described above, the JPL coherent laser absorption spectrometer operates at a frequency of about 2 microns and has similar technology needs. This system, however, is less resource intensive and also has the potential to work in concert with the GSFC laser sounder.

Prior to implementation of a flight hardware build, particularly for active sensors, laboratory measurement demonstration, horizontal path demonstration, and aircraft measurements with a representative version of the proposed instrument will be made to compare with measurements from in-situ sensors. In addition to their science calibration/validation function, these mission precursors will assist in the design process for the eventual space flight instrument.

Ocean Carbon Technology Requirements

Several measurements of importance to ocean working group representatives require active sensors. A lidar technique has been proposed to measure ocean bicarbonate, the major component of dissolved inorganic carbon. A study was also performed in the GSFC ISAL to develop an initial concept for a 532 and 1064 nm lidar that would measure particulates within the upper mixed layer of the oceans. Finally, an active fluorescence experiment using a pump and probe lidar with sources at 532 nm and 355 nm and detector at 685 nm has been demonstrated to measure photosynthetic parameters related to chlorophyll and biological productivity. Relative to the immediate goals and objectives of the GCCP, these observations are currently scoped as a series of aircraft flights. Improvements in spaceborne lidar technology are needed to fully utilize these as spaceborne sensors.

The ongoing SeaWiFS program and planned observations of passive fluorescence from MODIS are being used to study organic carbon in the open ocean. These types of observations need to be extended beyond the lifetime of these existing sensors. Furthermore, there is a renewed emphasis on coastal studies for tracking the movement of carbon between the land or rivers and the sea. These studies should be performed in the ultraviolet, visible, and near infrared using an instrument with a spatial resolution similar to MODIS (250 m or less) and a band selection tailored to sensing dissolved and particulate organic carbon, particularly in the near-shore environment. Such an

instrument would initially fly on an aircraft, but would ultimately be developed for the proposed ocean carbon space mission. The enhanced SeaWiFS type instrument would include bands for improved ocean productivity measurements (typically 660 and 680 nm) and bands in the ultraviolet for dissolved organic carbon. The technological challenges include selection of bands not generally used in land applications, improvements in sensor design, and the use of onboard data processing to optimize data retrieval. As with SeaWiFS, the spacecraft and instrument should accommodate routine lunar and solar calibrations. The ocean carbon mission would complement global observations from NPP/VIIRS.

In-situ instruments are particularly important for the planned GCCP measurement and instrument development activities and for the field campaigns and calibration/validation efforts that follow. Specific technologies are sought that improve the precision, accuracy, range, and reliability of ground-based measurements and of the aircraft and space missions they support. The miniaturization of drifter buoys with optical, percent CO₂, and nutrient sensors is one such improvement that has already been identified.

Biomass Observation Technology Requirements

The land working group identified a technology wedge that would enable new or improved measurements of biomass, biomass change, ecosystem disturbance, disturbance recovery, and primary productivity. A timetable was proposed that exploited existing or planned space assets, such as Landsat, SeaWiFS, EOS/Terra, and VCL, and allowed for development of new observational capabilities. In the near term, improved land cover algorithms that are more automated and merge data from multiple sensors are sought to extend observational capability over more biomes, disturbance types, and biomass ranges. Changes in biomass occur over a wide range of temporal and spatial scales and include responses to and recovery from disturbances and climate signals. Disturbances include both very rapid processes, such as fire and catastrophic storms, and more incremental changes from causes such as land use intensification, acid deposition, pests and pathogens, and human suppression of fire. As part of the proposed GCCP, space-based observations are therefore needed that embrace the full range of biomes so that global carbon assessments can be made.

- ◆ **Description:** A satellite mission that provides improved regional and global estimates of vegetation biomass and carbon stocks, studies the response of terrestrial ecosystems to major disturbances, and measures the rate of recovery
- ◆ **Instruments:** A P-band SAR operating at 0.44 GHz and a multi-track, 1.064 micron, imaging laser altimeter with a capability of resolving 0.5 m differences in vegetation height
- ◆ **Spacecraft:** A three-axis stabilized, nadir pointing spacecraft from the RSDO catalog modified to accommodate a large propulsion system and an X-band phased array

Key Technologies:
High resolution P-band polarimetric SAR, pixelated detectors, a high-accuracy attitude & position knowledge package, laser diode efficiency & lifetime improvements, & an S-band low power transceiver

Launch Date: FY 2011
Mission Life: 3 Years
Orbit: 400 km polar sun-synchronous with a 6:00 p.m. ascending node
Launch Vehicle: Delta II or equivalent class launch vehicle

Figure 9. High Density Biomass

- ◆ **Description:** A small satellite mission that measures the global concentration of carbon dioxide and oxygen in the lower troposphere
- ◆ **Instruments:** A pulsed, dual frequency, tunable laser sounder operating in the 1570 nm band for carbon dioxide detection and in the 770 nm band for oxygen detection
- ◆ **Spacecraft:** A low-cost, three-axis stabilized, nadir pointing spacecraft from the RSDO catalog with a propulsion system and appropriate subsystem modifications

Key Technologies:
1570 nm lidar sensor development, S-band low power transceiver

Launch Date: FY 2012
Mission Life: 3 Years
Orbit: 590 km circular sun-synchronous with a 7:00 a.m. or 7:00 p.m. ascending node
Launch Vehicle: Delta 2320-10 or equivalent class launch vehicle

Figure 10. Advanced Atmospheric CO₂

Technologies supporting identification of land cover itself are relatively mature. Moderate resolution, multispectral, passive optical sensors permit fine resolution mapping of land cover parameters, whereas coarse resolution, passive optical sensors allow the creation of dense spectral time series. However, further progress in determining global biomass and biomass change requires direct measurement of three-dimensional vegetation structures using other measurement techniques. In this regard, both broad-band and hyperspectral passive optical sensors, radar, active lasers/lidars, and bi-directional reflectance type instruments are worthy of further study. Hyperspectral measurements offer improved discrimination of land cover type, especially for low biomass systems. Synthetic aperture radar (SAR), on the other hand, enables repeated observations of boreal and tropical ecosystems over which acquisition of optical imagery is often precluded by cloud cover or darkness. For their part, lidars provide height or surface roughness images from which the magnitude of carbon stocks can be deduced, particularly for high biomass systems. A sensor fusion algorithm development effort is also needed to combine height information from VCL with existing land cover sensor data from Enhanced Thematic Mapper (ETM+), MODIS, and MISR to produce vegetation biomass and biomass change maps.

Specific technology needs have been identified for each of the above referenced sensor types and are described here. Hyperspectral imagers, potentially useful for low density biomass/coastal ocean carbon cycle measurements, will require much higher signal to noise ratios than those achieved for the EO-1 Hyperion instrument. In addition, large area focal plane arrays, large capacity onboard data recorders, and high rate downlink communications systems are needed to improve mission performance for a system with data rates approaching 700 Mbps. There is also a stated need for the development of an in-situ imaging hyperspectral spectrometer for algorithm development and validation of aircraft and spaceborne instruments. A high resolution P-band polarimetric SAR, consisting of a deployable antenna and an electronics module, is another proposed instrument that can make high density biomass measurements in concert with a single or dual frequency lidar. These lidars, more capable than the MBLA on VCL, require a significant technology investment to develop pixelated detectors for terrestrial biomass imaging. Detector options include conventional avalanche photodiodes, photon counting, or optical lens arrays. In addition to woody biomass (trees and shrubs), images could also be made of herbaceous biomass (grasslands) by adding a red channel to the single frequency lidar and shifting its near infrared channel to a shorter wavelength. The key technology for this dual frequency lidar is the selection and development of the optimal technique to provide a red channel between 650 and 680 nm. Candidates include frequency mixing, crystal doubling, and Raman shifting. Biomass lidars also rely on a high accuracy attitude and position knowledge package for precise geolocation

measurements that provide the required 1 to 2 arcsec post-processed attitude knowledge. Options for this ACS related hardware include a dual frequency global positioning system (GPS) with carrier phases on both frequencies along with a star tracker and a stable gyro, or an integrated attitude and position knowledge package. Finally, more advanced multi-angle and polarization type instrument simulators of MISR heritage need to be demonstrated via aircraft flights. Data from these flights must then be compared with in-situ calibration/validation measurements to assess performance.

5. LASER TECHNOLOGY READINESS

As proposed, the GCCP will utilize a significant number of lasers to meet its aircraft and space-based observational requirements. In particular, laser and lidar systems are envisioned that perform biomass imaging, atmospheric carbon dioxide profiling, and ocean carbon measurements. Recent difficulties with several laser/lidar missions under development have heightened awareness of the importance of technology readiness and comprehensive testing. A report from the Earth Science Independent Laser Review Panel summarizes key issues and recommendations.

In order to adequately assess the risk associated with active sensors under consideration for the baseline carbon cycle mission set, a laser/lidar benchmarking study was performed. This study compared key GCCP instrument design and performance parameters with those from previous or planned missions such as Shuttle Laser Altimeter (SLA), Lidar In-space Technology Experiment (LITE), Space Readiness Coherent Laser Experiment (SPARCLE), Geoscience Laser Altimeter System (GLAS), VCL, and Picasso-Cena. Instrument parameters included lifetime, orbit altitude, laser type, telescope size, mass, power, data rate, spot size, energy, wavelength, pulse length, pulse repetition frequency, and number of shots. It was concluded that, although there was clear heritage in many cases, GCCP requirements exceeded those of previous instruments in at least several of its key design or performance parameters.

In a further attempt to identify the state of technology readiness for some candidate laser/lidar systems, a detailed decomposition or component by component evaluation was made for single and dual frequency biomass imagers and for an atmospheric CO₂ laser sounder and differential absorption lidar. These assessments highlight instrument components and subsystems in need of advancement. In addition to the above specific laser/lidar instrument technologies, there is a set of generic or common elements that need attention. These include improvements in laser diode reliability and efficiency, development of better materials and coating damage test techniques, enhancements to performance modeling, and qualification of commercial fiber lasers and amplifiers for space-based remote sensing. A questionnaire was also prepared and distributed to select

atmosphere, ocean, and land science team members in order to collect related technology needs for aircraft and in-situ measurements of importance to carbon cycle calibration/validation activities. Both new equipment and improvements to existing instrumentation were solicited.

Laser Risk Mitigation

As a result of the referenced benchmarking studies and several laser review panel recommendations, a cursory risk mitigation strategy was developed at the program, mission, and instrument level for observations employing both active and passive sensors. At the program level, an architecture has been developed that includes the technology and instrument investments needed to enable the desired measurements. The technology development funding requested is significant and is detailed in the cost section of the GCCP. Alternate technology paths will also be pursued wherever feasible, and technology needs for missions beyond the proof-of-concept will be supported. Technology readiness will ultimately determine the order of the core flight missions. At the mission level, substantial mass and power margins will be maintained for new active and passive instrument systems and adequate redundancy will be incorporated into all mission critical flight systems. Moreover, comprehensive testing at the system level before acceptance for flight is viewed as a critical performance assurance element and will be allotted appropriate financial and schedule resources. Finally, a number of steps will be taken to reduce risk at the instrument level. These include the following:

- (1) A technology readiness level of 6 (out of 9) is proposed before the instrument implementation phase can begin;
- (2) An engineering test unit is included as part of the flight instrument development program for active sensors;
- (3) Life testing will be performed on all critical mechanisms and laser system components;
- (4) Existing technology programs will be leveraged to the fullest extent possible.

Carbon cycle mission concept studies, described previously, indicate that the present list of candidate spacecrafts can accommodate the instruments and observations described in the previous paragraphs with minor modifications. Existing launch vehicles and ground systems, though not optimal, are also adequate for all requirements, but the balance between distributed and centralized data systems needs to be explored. The greatest challenge lies in the development of active and passive sensors, particularly lidars, to perform extended global measurements. A coordinated and well-funded technology program to improve performance and reduce risk is proposed. Careful attention must also be paid to scaling of aircraft instrumentation for space flight. Recent experience demonstrates that this transition imposes

some technological hurdles that must be addressed early in the development phase.

6. CRITICAL DEPENDENCIES

The science and technology development program outlined in the previous sections make a number of assumptions regarding the continuation of existing and planned NASA programs and assets made available through collaborations with other federal agencies. Some of the programs which will be of particular importance to carbon cycle research include: the Aqua, Aura, VCL, Landsat, Global Precipitation Mission (GPM), and NPOESS Preparatory Program (NPP) missions, including data processing, distribution and validation; the NSIPP and SIMBIOS programs; certain hydrological cycle observations which are key to the carbon cycle, including soil moisture, soil freeze-thaw state, and ocean salinity; and the availability of the NASA Data Assimilation Office (DAO), certain NASA aircraft, the AERONET array of sun photometers and the NOAA CO₂ flask sampling network and shiptime.

Anticipated Outcome

A number of information and data products are anticipated as a result of the GCCP that will be of use for decision and policy making as well as for resource management. The precise timing of some of these deliverables, particularly those requiring new space-borne sensors, will depend on the technical progress made during the development phases and the measurement approach and technologies chosen for deployment. This is discussed in detail above. The timing of the achievements listed below is based roughly on the notional mission set shown above.

- (1) Significant results and progress in the observational component of the GCCP can be achieved within the first five years by accelerating NASA's participation in the NACP, and by the development of high spatial resolution global land cover products employing Landsat to map areas of vegetation disturbance and document their rate of recovery. By resolving concern about technological readiness and then accelerating the deployment of vegetation canopy lidar technology, we also could obtain vegetation height and structural information to produce the first, globally consistent estimate of terrestrial above-ground biomass. These and other anticipated deliverables from the GCCP are:
- (2) The NACP to be conducted in 2004-2006 in cooperation with other U.S. agencies will quantify the North American region's carbon sources and sinks, describe the processes controlling changes in them, and document North America's contribution to the northern hemisphere carbon sink. This will lead to better understanding of the underlying mechanisms of carbon storage and release and the

roles of particular sectors and sub-regions. NASA will also be able to take advantage of the field program to establish and calibrate the field infrastructure that will be needed to validate future space-based observations of aerosols, CO₂, ocean carbon, and terrestrial biomass.

- (3) By 2006, an in situ network of vertical CO₂ profilers optimized for long term operation and support of future satellite validation activities will be in place.
- (4) By 2006, the first full report on the state of the U.S. carbon cycle, including terrestrial ecosystems, adjacent oceans, and the overlying atmosphere, will be produced jointly with other U.S. agencies, the science community, and other stakeholders.
- (5) By 2004-2005, an analysis of land cover change in North America for the ten-year period from 1990-2000 will be completed. By the end of 2006, land cover change in North America extended to include the period 2001-2005.
- (6) By late 2005, the first quantitative measurements of vegetation height and vertical structure from a space-based lidar (VCL), and local-area biomass estimates will be generated. By 2007, the first internally consistent estimates of global above-ground biomass for the Earth's forests based on a robust sampling strategy using this space-based lidar will be available. In addition, the new capability will allow us to demonstrate and evaluate the ability of this technology to measure biomass change over time for a few selected sites and short periods of time.

In the second 5-year phase of the GCCP, we will deliver observational capabilities to provide high spatial resolution atmospheric CO₂ data sets that will reduce regional uncertainties in source and sink strengths from the current 100% uncertainty to around 25% and will allow us to follow the seasonal and interannual variation in these sources and sinks and correlate them with climate-related phenomena such as ENSO. In late 2008, we will accurately locate and quantify land and ocean surface and sinks of CO₂ with regional resolution (e.g., for regions about the size of Texas) using improved inverse models and new global satellite observations of atmospheric CO₂ concentrations. We will deliver an enhanced ocean carbon data set that will permit us to significantly improve our characterization of the export of carbon to the deep sea. Carbon export to the deep sea occurs as particle sinking (the "biological pump") and subsidence of cold CO₂-bearing water (the "solubility pump"). Additional carbon fluxes to the ocean are organic matter and dissolved carbon in terrestrial runoff. Schemes for estimating these fluxes will be developed using a combination of in situ and satellite observations and models. In phase two, we will also launch advanced terrestrial biomass observational capabilities that will yield comprehensive estimates of biomass and biomass change for all terrestrial biomes, resolved at sub-regional scale, and

will enable quantitative assessment of vegetation disturbance and recovery rates.

Throughout the GCCP, we can engage in focused activities that improve our analysis tools and data sets. Tools will be developed to utilize new space observations and process models. Tools for scaling regional-level understanding to the global level will also be developed. Only at the global scale can we fully understand the transport mechanisms and rates between the land and ocean, and the impact of land-use and climate change on the global carbon cycle. These new scientific analysis tools will lead to decision support tools that decision makers can use to explore impacts of energy policies, land use policies, and climate change policies on management options. Resource managers will have more efficient and reliable methods for inventorying forests, rangelands, and croplands and assessing the impact of various management practices on crop yields, timber volume, and soil fertility

7. SUMMARY

The above investments in new global observations and related satellite data analysis will yield solid, quantitative information on the global distribution, strength, and variability of carbon sources and sinks; and the processes that regulate the fluxes and transformations between the land, ocean, and atmosphere. Error budgets in the global carbon balance will be significantly reduced, and policy-makers will have a better understanding of where the global hot spots of carbon uptake and release are. When assimilated into integrated Earth climate system models, these observations also will yield useful predictions of future atmospheric CO₂ and CH₄ concentrations, and climate change. Projections of future climate change and the scenarios used to make informed assessments will be significantly improved.

Figure 11. GCCP Phased Deliverables

8. UPDATE

Since the preparation of the NASA Global Carbon Cycle Plan to NASA Headquarters in June 2001, there have been a number of beneficial developments. The plan was included with proposed advances in climate modeling and computer technology in the NASA Climate Change Research Proposal to OMB on September 12, 2001. Planning for NASA Climate Change Research is still on-going. This material has contributed to the future planning for the Earth Science Enterprise Roadmaps to answer the most important Earth science questions. The implementation strategy for the North American Carbon Program is underway and will almost certainly contain major elements of the plan. Finally, the selection of the Orbiting Carbon Observatory as an Earth Science System Pathfinder means that the first mission to measure CO₂ column will soon be a reality. The additional selections of Aquarius and Hydros will also provide measurements identified as critical dependencies.

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Dr. Jan Gervin has been a remote sensing manager and research scientist with NASA for over 29 years, holding positions of increasing responsibility at GSFC and Kennedy Space Center. She is currently Project Formulation Manager for

NASA's *Global Carbon Cycle Plan*, a multi-mission program which will examine the seasonal, interannual and geographic distribution of carbon in Earth's atmosphere, oceans and on land. Previously she oversaw the development, delivery and launch of MOPITT (*Measurements of Pollution in the Troposphere*), one of five instruments on the first Earth Observing System (EOS) platform Terra. She was Instruments Manager for the EOS Atmospheric Chemistry Program at NASA Headquarters, managing the definition and development of instruments on the third EOS platform Aura. Dr. Gervin served on the Space Station Task Force at NASA Headquarters, as the Earth Sciences Representative to the Space Station Program Office at Johnson Space Center, and as Science Advocate and later Manager for the Attached Payloads Accommodation Equipment on the manned Space Station. As a science program manager in the Hydrological Sciences Branch and Eastern Regional Remote Sensing Applications Center at GSFC she designed, developed and managed remote sensing research and applications projects with the US Army Corps of Engineers, Environmental Protection Agency, and the states of Delaware, Virginia and Illinois in suburban land use, flood mitigation, wetland mapping and forest management. Dr. Gervin received the B.A. in Physics from Bucknell University (1969), M.S. in Physics from the University of Florida (1971), and PhD in Engineering specializing in Remote Sensing Hydrology from the University of Maryland (1992).

Dr. Charles R. McClain has been a research scientist at NASA GSFC since 1978 and has specialized in the processing and analysis of satellite ocean color data. During the 1980s, he was a co-investigator in the Nimbus-7 Coastal Zone Color Scanner global reprocessing and lead the development of the SEAPAK and PC-SEAPAK ocean color data processing and analysis systems which were distributed to the ocean color community. He was the SeaWiFS calibration and validation manager from the beginning of the project through the third global reprocessing in 2000 and managed the development of the SeaWiFS Data Analysis System (SeaDAS) which is provided to the satellite ocean color user community. He also served as SeaWiFS project manager for the first three years of on-orbit operations and has been the SeaWiFS project scientist since 1996. He lead the Sensor Intercomparison and Merger for Biological and Interdisciplinary Oceanic Studies (SIMBIOS) formulation effort, actively managed the program from 1997 through 2000, and remains the SIMBIOS project scientist. In 2001, he led a NASA-wide carbon cycle research and technology formulation effort and is currently involved in multi-agency planning efforts for ocean carbon research and the North American Carbon Program. More recently, he has been involved in the NPOESS Preparatory Project (NPP) ocean color/SST data processing system formulation.

Dr. Forrest G. Hall is Senior Scientist at the Joint Center for Earth Systems Technology at the University of

Maryland, Baltimore County. He is located at the NASA GSFC's Laboratory for Terrestrial Physics where he currently serves as Science Advisor in Goddard's Office of Global Carbon Studies. Dr. Hall recently co-lead with Dr. Chuck McClain of NASA GSFC, NASA Headquarters Carbon Cycle Science Study that involved key carbon cycle scientists, agency leaders in carbon cycle science, as well as NASA Center scientists. The results of this study, recommendations for a NASA's carbon cycle research program, are published in McClain et al., 2002. Trained as a mathematical physicist, Dr. Hall has published over 30 papers in the last 10 years in areas ranging from remote sensing of terrestrial ecosystems to carbon cycle investigations. Dr. Hall has extensive technical management experience. In addition to being the BOREAS Project Manager, Principal Investigator for ISLSCP Initiative II, he has served as Project Manager of the FIFE Project, Chief of the Scene Analysis Branch at the Johnson Space Center, and Project Scientist of the Large Area Crop Inventory Project.

Mr. Paul Caruso is presently a Senior Systems Engineer at Swales Aerospace located in Beltsville, Maryland. He is retired from NASA GSFC where he formally held a range of management and technical positions. His areas of expertise include mission formulation, spacecraft and instrument systems development, thermal design and analysis, fluid dynamics, and integration and environmental testing. He received an M.S. degree in Aeronautical Engineering from the Pennsylvania State University and a B.S. degree in Engineering Physics from Loyola College in Baltimore, Maryland.